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TRAINING OF TEACHERS-DEFECTOLOGISTS IN THE CONDITIONS OF MODERN LABOR MIGRATION

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У дослідженні теоретично обґрунтовано й експериментально перевірено ключові аспекти підготовки вчителів-дефектологів (логопедів) до роботи з дітьми з особливими освітніми потребами в умовах сучасних закладів інклюзивної освіти.

Аналіз сучасного стану здійснення корекційно-розвивальної роботи з молодшими школярами з особливими освітніми потребами – порушеннями інтелектуального розвитку різного ступеня тяжкості, засвідчило існування певного кола проблем.

Було з'ясовано, що залишається гострою проблема трактування порушень мовлення в обраній категорії дітей у межах сучасної логопедичної психолого-педагогічної класифікації, проведення комплексного клінічного скрінінгу. Вже на етапі діагностування сучасні вчителі-дефектологи мають недостатній педагогічний інструментарій для встановлення та виявлення відповідного виду порушень психофізичного розвитку.

Сучасна система інклюзивної освіти вимагає багатопрофільності знань вчителів, асистентів-вчителів для здійснення ефективного навчально-педагогічного діяльності з обраною категорією учнів не стільки в сучасному спеціальному освітньому просторі, скільки в інклюзивній освіті.

Вимогами сьогодення є підготовка «універсальних» вчителів-дефектологів для закладів інклюзивної освіти. З огляду на масову трудову міграцію, зумовлену нестійкою соціально-економічною ситуацією в країні, на ринку праці актуальною залишається постійна нехватка кваліфікованих вчителів, для роботи з дітьми з особливими освітніми потребами.

Проведений аналіз навчальної документації (навчальних планів, робочих навчальних програм) у ВЗО щодо підготовки студентів спеціальності 016 Спеціальна освіта виявив відсутність відповідних навчальних дисциплін, зміст яких розкриває прикладні аспекти формування й корекції мовленнєвої діяльності дітей з особливими освітніми потребами, які б сприяли опануванню студентами теоретико-практичними знаннями про специфіку здійснення корекційно-розвивальної (логокорекційної) роботи з обраною категорією дітей.

Сприяння розв'язанню цієї проблеми є необхідність введення в навчальні плани закладів вищої освіти, які готують фахівців за спеціальністю 016 Спеціальна освіта, до циклу вибіркових дисциплін професійно-практичної підготовки майбутніх психокорекційних педагогів і логопедів відповідної дисципліни (наприклад – «Спеціальна методика розвитку мовлення»), чи включення окремих її модулів (розділів) до інших споріднених дисциплін

Ключові слова: трудова міграція, вчителі-дефектологи, спеціальна освіта, інклюзивна освіта, особливі діти

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1. Introduction

Modern educational policy requires the development of new improved educational content. Such an educational environment has created a high motivation for all children. It made a significant contribution to the development of a humane society, based on equality.

A modern school should prepare a child, including those with mental or physical disabilities (MPD), in accordance with his/her abilities and capabilities for independent life and adaptation in society and the active participation of the child in the life of the family, society, and the state.

2. Literature review

Speech disorders are the most common category of disorders, which can be both isolated and against the background of other developmental disorders. In the studies of O. Boriak, in particular, it is noted, that speech disorders in children with special educational needs, in most cases, are primary developmental disorders, which is thoroughly disclosed in studies [1]. The author notes that speech disorders usually reflect the level of cognitive development.

The specificity of speech disorders (SoSD) in children with intellectual disabilities (DIP) is determined primarily by the peculiarities of higher nervous activity and mental development. These features are the main

factors of speech underdevelopment in this category of children [1].

The modern research has identified the specifics of neurogenesis and psychogenesis of various forms of intellectual disabilities – mild, moderate and profound degrees of mental retardation [2]. The authors singled out the levels of speech development in intellectual disabilities, identified their symptoms and dependence on intellectual impairment [3]. Most studies have identified levels of cognition and learning abilities of children with speech disorders on the background of intellectual disabilities [4]. Scientists have studied the state of health of a selected category of people, its impact on general physical capabilities, the prospects for further independent socialization [5]. Modern researchers have identified the main areas of training to work with a selected category of people in both educational institutions and social rehabilitation institutions [6]. Scientists have characterized the specifics of medical-psychological-pedagogical approaches to work, and identified requirements for the quality of professionals working with a selected category of people [7].

It was found, that the mechanisms of speech disorders that occur in intellectual disorders are determined not only by general, diffuse brain underdevelopment, which causes systemic speech underdevelopment, but also by the local pathology of areas, directly related to speech, which further complicates the manifestations of speech disorders [8].

This complicates or makes impossible the socio-psychological adaptation of children. This complicates their educational and professional future. According to scientists, the nature of speech development goes through certain stages: a child's speech first develops as a result of the perception of adult speech by children and their own speech activity; secondly, children's orientation to speech activity creates preconditions for speech self-development; Finally, the formation of language generalizations in children and the basic understanding of speech phenomena play a leading role in their speech development [9, 10].

The development of speech in children with impaired mental and / or physical development is one of the most difficult and insufficiently solved speech therapy problems.

The most numerous group among the people with mental and physical development disorders are people with intellectual disabilities – mental retardation.

3. The aim and objectives of the study

The aim of the study was to investigate the current state of preparation of modern teacher-defectologists; definition and substantiation of directions of preparation and professional development of specialists for work with children with special educational needs in the conditions of modern educational space.

To achieve this aim, the following objectives were set:

1. To conduct a survey to identify the current status of professional skills of modern defectologists (speech therapists) to diagnose existing disorders of psychophysical development in children with special educational needs.

2. To define and substantiate effective directions of improvement of the process of preparation of future specialists-defectologists in the conditions of modern institutions of higher education.

4. Materials and methods

Research Focus. The feasibility and relevance of the study in view of the requirements of the present is substantiated. All aspects were considered at a new level, taking into account the requirements for specialists of the defectological profile in both special and inclusive education institutions.

Methodology of Research. The relevance and prospects of studying this problem are due to: an increase in the birth rate of children with mental retardation, in which a serious violation of physical development or a secondary disorder is diagnosed against the background of other disorders. The main task is a one-factor approach to the diagnosis, formation and correction of speech activity of mentally retarded children. The content of the work on the development of speech is not defined. In special educational institutions for children with mental retardation there is no correction software. There are no scientifically substantiated methods for the formation and correction of speech activity of mentally retarded children in the complex of impacts at all its levels, on all components; which leads to a low level of effectiveness of speech therapy correction. It is necessary to develop a comprehensive rational system for the diagnosis, formation and correction of the speech development of mentally retarded children.

In the course of the study, a survey was conducted, which involved 120 speech therapists, defectologists from 23 special institutions of general secondary education: schools, boarding schools, educational and rehabilitation centers in 12 regions of the country.

Tutors were offered a questionnaire with questions, among which it was necessary to note: what terminology is used by specialists to identify speech disorders in students with intellectual disabilities (speech therapy conclusions in speech cards, based on PMPC conclusions, IRC decisions, conclusions, based on internal speech therapy examination); what methodological support of the correctional and developmental process on the ground (names of programs, manuals, didactic materials, used by practitioners); to identify forms of organization of the educational process that are common during correctional and developmental work; to name the leading directions of correctional and developmental work at different age stages (common in primary classes).

The results of the survey were processed using the methods of mathematical statistics – determining the percentage of similarity of responses.

According to the results of the survey, it remains clear, that the problem of diagnosing and interpreting the types of psychophysical development disorders remains acute, given the complexity and combination of their different types.

It is revealed, that 84.6 % of defect teachers have some difficulties in using and applying defective terminology within the framework of psychological and pedagogical classification, when defectological conclusions

are made regarding the definition of speech disorders in primary school children with special educational needs.

Regarding the software-methodological support of correctional and developmental work, it was found, that the majority of specialists in their work use modified programs for children with various disorders of psychophysical development (by primary disorder) within the International Classification of Diseases (ICD) 11 views (33.6 %); adapted programs for children of primary school age with special educational needs (24.6 %), author's educational programs, approved by methodological associations and pedagogical councils of educational institutions (41.8 %).

In most cases, teaching materials are materials for the above programs, adapted by teacher-pathologists to work with children with special educational needs.

5. Discussion

Summarizing the above, we can say that there are significant contradictions regarding the use of appropriate defectology terminology, the lack of appropriate software and methodological support for the process of correction and development work with a selected category of children.

An acute problem is the form of organization of correction and development lessons, during which proper correction and development work is carried out, since within the classroom-lesson system there are difficulties in the complete set of groups for correction and development lessons (different levels of speech activity development, manifestations of speech disorders in students from one class), the implementation of individual correction and development work (correction and development of emotional-volitional, cognitive, speech).

This necessitates another direction of search work – analysis of the state of preparation and professional development of specialists to work with children with special educational needs in the context of special and / or inclusive education.

Today, in most institutions of higher education of the country, students are trained in the direction of 016 Special Education (by nosology, where more common is the training of students in the specialty of speech therapy, psychocorrectional pedagogy (oligophrenopedagogy).

The analysis of educational documentation (curricula, work bulk programs) in ZVO on preparation of students of specialty 016 Special education (Psychocorrectional pedagogics), (Logopedics), (Oligophrenopedagogics. Logopedics) with the purpose of revealing disciplines, content of which work reveals aspects of work conditions of an inclusive class.

The analysis of academic disciplines revealed the study of individual issues, which mainly relate to the development (in various disorders of psychophysical development), correction and development work with children with special educational needs (determination

of the main directions of implementation of correction and development work in the formation and correction of speech, speech activities and psychophysical development).

The analysis of educational professional programs for the training of specialists in specialty 016 Special education revealed the lack of appropriate educational disciplines that would help students to acquire theoretical and practical knowledge about the specifics of implementation of corrective-developmental work with a selected category of children. Today there are no educational institutions in the country that train specialists in the field of 016 Special education (inclusive education), which makes it impossible to carry out this field of work at the required level. This is a problem that needs to be addressed at the state level, which we see as facilitating the need to introduce into the curricula a cycle of selective disciplines of future practitioners of defectology.

An alternative is to organize the work of a student problem group or a student scientific group in this direction. The preparation of students will not only improve the professional level of future specialists, but will also affect the effectiveness of further correctional and development work with children.

6. Conclusions

During the study it was found out.

1. Identifying the current state of professional skills of modern defectologists (speech therapists) to diagnose existing disorders of psychophysical development in children with special educational needs revealed a number of problems at the level of determining the type of disorders of psychophysical development. Modern teachers of defectologists operate with different approaches and, accordingly, with different terminology in defining a particular disorder of psychophysical development.

At the same time, experts of inclusive-resource centers provide rather vague definition and recommendations for individual corrective-development work.

2. In the course of the study, effective directions of improvement of the process of preparation of future specialists-defectologists in the conditions of modern higher education institutions were identified and substantiated. It is suggested to introduce into the curricula the cycle of selective disciplines of professional and practical training of future pedagogues (speech therapists), or to include some of its modules (sections) in other related disciplines.

The study does not exhaust all aspects of the problem outlined. Further scientific research may be studies, related to the "need" of using the developed professional skills of modern defect teachers in the context of modern labor migration. This applies to cases, where professionals work in the specialty or related specialties (governor, tutor, etc.).

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